

CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AFTER COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate clinical and laboratory changes in patients with rheumatoid arthritis after COVID-19..

Introduction

Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic autoimmune inflammatory disease characterized by erosive-destructive joint changes, functional limitation, and reduced quality of life. COVID-19 infection may intensify immune inflammation, deepen cytokine imbalance, and worsen the clinical course of rheumatoid arthritis. Therefore, assessment of the clinical and laboratory features of rheumatoid arthritis in the post-COVID period remains highly relevant.

Objective of the study

To evaluate clinical and laboratory changes in patients with rheumatoid arthritis after COVID-19.

Materials and methods

The study was carried out during 2020–2022. A total of 120 patients with rheumatoid arthritis were included: the main group consisted of 60 patients who had recovered from COVID-19, and the control group consisted of 60 patients without a history of COVID-19. Disease activity was assessed using DAS28, while pain syndrome and functional status were evaluated using the HAQ scale. Laboratory investigations included C-reactive protein and selected indicators reflecting immune inflammation.

Results

In patients with rheumatoid arthritis after COVID-19, clinical and laboratory activity of the disease was significantly higher than in the control group. In particular, the level of C-reactive protein (CRP) was 38.39 ± 14.22 mg/L in the main group versus 28.15 ± 5.58 mg/L in the control group, and the difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The DAS28 index was 5.8 ± 0.32 in the main group and 4.6 ± 0.45 in the control group, indicating significantly higher disease activity in post-COVID patients ($p < 0.001$). The HAQ index, reflecting functional status, was also higher in the main group (1.27 ± 0.04) than in the control group (1.02 ± 0.03), which confirmed a significantly greater degree of functional limitation ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Main indicators in the study and control groups

Indicator	Main group (n=60)	Control group (n=60)	p
CRP, mg/L	38.39±14.22	28.15±5.58	<0.001
DAS28	5.8±0.32	4.6±0.45	<0.001
HAQ	1.27±0.04	1.02±0.03	<0.001
Myalgia, %	28	18	<0.001
Rheumatoid nodules, %	12.7	9.4	<0.001
Carditis, %	9.7	7.2	<0.001

Analysis of clinical manifestations showed that myalgia was observed in 28% of patients in the main group and in 18% of patients in the control group. Rheumatoid nodules were recorded in 12.7% and 9.4% of cases, respectively, whereas carditis was identified in 9.7% and 7.2% of cases.

Conclusion

In patients with rheumatoid arthritis after COVID-19, inflammatory activity and disease severity were higher than in the control group.

Significantly elevated DAS28, CRP, and HAQ values in post-COVID patients confirmed increased clinical and laboratory activity of the disease.

The obtained results indicate the need to strengthen clinical and laboratory monitoring in patients with rheumatoid arthritis during the post-COVID period.

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